

POLITICAL SCIENCES

REDIFINING POWER: EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF NEW POPULIST MOVEMENTS ON GLOBAL DIPLOMACY

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Abstract

This study delves into the evolving landscape of global diplomacy in the context of the surge in new populist movements across the globe. At the heart of this exploration is the premise that these movements, characterized by their appeal to popular discontent with the status quo and their often unconventional leadership styles, are redefining the traditional paradigms of power and influence on the international stage. Through a comprehensive analysis of case studies from various regions, the paper examines how these movements challenge existing diplomatic norms, influence international relations, and reshape the strategies of both state and non-state actors in the global arena.

Keywords: Populist Movements, Global Diplomacy, International Cooperation, Diplomatic Norms.

The rise of populism in various regions of the world is rooted in a set of objective challenges that societies are currently confronting. These challenges include the migration of economic growth centers, the widening gap of inequality associated with globalization, the automation of production, and the rapid advancement of new technologies. These economic and technological shifts have contributed to a sense of uncertainty and insecurity among segments of the population. The fear of losing cultural identity is another significant factor driving populism. The ease of transport and communication in the modern era has facilitated a massive influx of migrants seeking refuge from war, repression, poverty, and climate change. This has sparked concerns among certain groups about the preservation of their cultural identity in the face of such demographic changes. The ideological gap between cosmopolitan elites, who endorse and benefit from the new trends in globalization and technology, and those who feel left behind or disoriented by these changes is a crucial aspect of the populist surge. This divide exacerbates a sense of disenchantment and lack of confidence in the future among certain segments of the population. Additionally, the rise in high-profile terrorist attacks has created an environment where demagogues can exploit fears to incite xenophobia and Islamophobia. Security concerns have been manipulated for political gain, further contributing to the populist wave. Addressing the rise of populism requires a comprehensive approach that considers the economic, cultural, and technological dimensions of the challenges at hand. Policymakers need to engage with issues such as economic inequality, cultural identity, and the impact of technological advancements to foster a more inclusive and stable global political landscape.

The surge of populism observed in democratic nations, including France, over the past two decades has prompted scholarly discussions on the reasons behind its intensification, the various forms it takes, and the programmatic guidelines it follows. Scholars note that populism tends to become more prominent in periods of historical change when traditional political systems face crises, social norms are disrupted, familiar mean-

ings are lost, and a new world is emerging with uncertainties about its nature. Populism thrives in such situations, constructing its discourse around ideas that may be perceived as illusory and unrealistic. Populist movements often promise sweeping changes, presenting themselves as a bridge between the old and the new while maintaining a distinct identity.

In times of upheaval and uncertainty, populism tends to gain traction by tapping into the anxieties and aspirations of a population seeking direction in the face of profound social and political changes. The promise of change, often anchored in simple and straightforward narratives, appeals to those grappling with the complexities and uncertainties of a shifting societal landscape.

Understanding the dynamics of populism requires a nuanced analysis of the broader socio-political context, as well as an exploration of how populist leaders frame their messages in response to the challenges and uncertainties present in times of significant change. The relationship between the crisis of established political systems, the erosion of traditional social norms, and the emergence of populism underscores the complex interplay of factors that contribute to the rise of populist movements.

France

France is one of those countries that, through its revolutionary struggle, made a great contribution to the spread of republican values around the world and proved that principles such as freedom, democracy, justice are an integral part of the cultural DNA of the French nation. Nevertheless, right-wing populism found its voters in this environment. The right-wing populist "National Rally" (until June 1, 2018, "National Front") not only attracts supporters, but also lures away the electorate of both right-wing and left-wing parties. What strategies contribute to this success?

The history of the party began in the 1970s, when France entered a period of instability. The "Golden Age" of the Fifth Republic, also called the time of the four Ps, came to an end.

FOUR "P"

Peace (paix)

Prosperity

Full time (plein emploi)

Progress

The emergence of populist sentiments in France was marked by a confluence of economic challenges, social stratification, and growing discontent exacerbated by immigration. Unemployment and social divisions replaced the optimism of the past, intensifying public dissatisfaction. The failures of Mitterrand's socialist government, particularly the inability to implement slogans like "Change Life" and "Break with Capitalism," further eroded trust in the political establishment.

Against this backdrop, French politician Jean-Marie Le Pen seized the opportunity to tap into the prevailing discontent. He founded a party that positioned itself as an alternative to both the left and the traditional right, presenting a populist narrative. Le Pen's party called for the establishment of a Sixth Republic, advocating for a transfer of power from the political elite to the common people. This appeal resonated with those disillusioned by the perceived shortcomings of the existing political order.

The promise of a new republic underpinned by the empowerment of the common people provided a rallying point for those seeking change and an alternative to the established political forces. The rise of this populist movement reflected a broader trend where disillusionment with the status quo fueled the emergence of political alternatives that presented themselves as champions of the people against the perceived failures of the mainstream political establishment.

The National Rally successfully garnered support from the traditional right-wing party electorate, capitalizing on a set of compelling reasons. The party's rallying cry to "defend the national identity, values, and traditions of French civilization and return France to its national sovereignty, back to a Europe of independent nations" resonated strongly amid the perceived inadequacies of long-standing mainstream parties that had struggled to address the challenges of the contemporary era.

At a time when the nation-state model faced challenges from the influx of migrants from the Middle East and the constraints of international sovereignty imposed by European integration, the National Rally, under the charismatic leadership of Jean-Marie Le Pen, provided a distinct alternative. The party tapped into the concerns of right-wing voters who felt that the foundations of the nation-state were being eroded, particularly by the impact of immigration and the diminishing autonomy within the context of European integration.

The allure of the National Rally lay in its promise to protect and rejuvenate the national identity, uphold traditional values, and restore France's sovereignty. Against the backdrop of perceived shortcomings in addressing these issues by established political forces, the National Rally emerged as a dynamic force capable of channeling the frustrations and aspirations of a segment of the electorate seeking a departure from the status quo. This charismatic appeal, coupled with a platform centered on national pride and independence, proved compelling for right-wing voters grappling with the

challenges of a rapidly changing socio-political landscape.

Since the 1990s, the National Rally has seen an influx of former supporters of leftist forces, particularly individuals worried about their socio-economic prospects. For this group of citizens, the immigrant population has come to be perceived as the source of various troubles and challenges, effectively replacing the capitalist as the focal point of their concerns. This shift in perception has resonated strongly among many young people within this demographic.

Anti-migration slogans put forth by the National Rally have found significant traction, reflecting the sentiments and grievances of its supporters. In response to these concerns, the party has proposed a series of measures aimed at addressing immigration-related issues. These measures are likely tailored to appeal to the anxieties of those who feel that their socio-economic well-being is under threat.

The National Rally's position on immigration often aligns with its broader narrative of defending national identity, values, and traditions. By framing immigration as a central challenge, the party seeks to position itself as a defender of the interests and concerns of its supporters, appealing to both those who may have traditionally aligned with right-wing politics and those who were once supporters of leftist forces but have shifted their allegiance due to economic apprehensions. This nuanced approach allows the National Rally to construct a coalition of diverse supporters with shared concerns about the impact of immigration on socio-economic conditions.

Prohibit the naturalization of illegal migrants;

Reduce legal migration to 10,000 people per year;

Simplify the process of deporting refugees;

Establish French citizenship as a privilege for the French people.

An integral element of the National Rally's positioning is the claim to be the sole party in France that advocates for the interests of the "ordinary Frenchman," particularly those facing economic challenges such as poverty or unemployment. Jean-Marie Le Pen targets approximately 10% of the French population who fall into this category. This emphasis on representing the concerns of the socioeconomically vulnerable is a crucial aspect of the party's narrative.

An examination of the composition of National Rally voters substantiates the relevance of the party's proposed measures. Approximately one-third of the voters belong to the working class, with an additional 20% comprising agricultural workers. Additionally, around 40% of the party's supporters have low or medium income levels, while only 11% have high incomes. This demographic breakdown aligns with the party's emphasis on championing the interests of those facing economic difficulties.

Geographically, the distribution of votes is uneven, with notable support coming from departments in the North, East, and South-East of France. These areas often experience declining industrial production or have a higher proportion of immigrants in the population. The National Rally's popularity in these regions suggests that its appeal resonates particularly strongly

in areas grappling with economic challenges or undergoing demographic shifts, reinforcing its image as a defender of the concerns of the "ordinary Frenchman" in the face of such difficulties.

The National Rally experienced notable successes in parliamentary elections during the latter half of the 1990s and the early 2000s, securing 12-15% of the votes. However, the party achieved a significant breakthrough in the 2012 presidential race when its leader garnered almost 18%, translating to approximately 6.4 million votes.

Although the party has faced challenges and a weakening of its positions following changes in key figures, recent developments in France, coupled with public sentiment, present an opportunity for the National Rally to regain strength. Socio-economic tensions, exemplified by the yellow vest movement in 2018, highlighted issues of poverty and inequality in the country. Additionally, anti-immigrant sentiments have been fueled by a series of terrorist attacks, such as those in Paris in 2015 and Nice in 2016, along with events in late October and early November 2020 related to Muslim visitors. This agenda provides the National Rally with a chance to expand its electorate and promote its ideas.

USA.

Drawing a parallel with the election of Donald Trump in the United States, his victory was marked by divisive rhetoric targeting Mexican immigrants, Muslim refugees, and various racial and ethnic minorities, alongside overt male chauvinism. This led to a robust human rights response in the U.S., with diverse segments of society, including activist groups, journalists, lawyers, judges, and individual citizens, mobilizing against these ideologies. Similarly, the National Rally's agenda may face resistance from various quarters in French society, especially from those advocating for tolerance, inclusivity, and human rights.

During his presidency, Donald Trump retained the ability to implement regressive initiatives through executive orders. These initiatives included efforts to deport individuals without considering their deep roots in the United States, reviving mass criminal incarceration practices, weakening police oversight, and restricting global funding for women's reproductive health. Despite facing powerful resistance, Trump managed to push through some of these measures.

For example, there were successful efforts to largely halt damage caused by discriminatory policies against Muslims seeking entry to the United States or seeking asylum, attempts to dismantle the healthcare guarantee system, and the ban on transgender individuals serving in the military. The resistance, comprising various groups such as activists, journalists, lawyers, judges, and concerned citizens, played a crucial role in mitigating the impact of regressive policies. In some instances, efforts were successful in preventing the deportation of immigrants who had been living in the United States for an extended period.

While Trump's executive orders posed challenges to progressive values, the robust resistance demonstrated the importance of collective activism and advocacy in upholding principles of inclusivity, human

rights, and social justice. The ability of civil society to mobilize against regressive policies played a vital role in mitigating the potential damage caused by certain initiatives during Trump's presidency.

During Rex Tillerson's tenure as Secretary of State, there was a notable shift away from actively promoting human rights in foreign policy, and a substantial reduction in the overall U.S. presence in the world. Tillerson's management of the State Department included significant downsizing, leaving many key positions vacant, terminating several experienced foreign service officers, cutting budgets, and allowing the Foreign Service to languish. This approach led to a sense of disillusionment among career diplomats and mid-level managers, prompting many to resign due to the perceived lack of prospects.

Despite these challenges, some individuals within the State Department, motivated by a commitment to human rights, made efforts to safeguard the protections that had been integral to American foreign policy for decades. These individuals, often with support from Congress, worked to prevent a complete disregard for human rights principles. While the overall direction of the State Department seemed to diminish its role as a system-forming vector of American foreign policy, pockets of resilience within the department persisted.

In instances where President Trump engaged with autocratic leaders, those individuals within the State Department who still valued human rights sought to uphold these principles, occasionally finding support from Congress. One notable example was the threat of targeted sanctions against the Burmese military implicated in the ethnic cleansing of the Rohingya Muslim minority. The efforts of these individuals within the State Department, who remained committed to human rights, played a role in ensuring that Washington continued to assert a stance on human rights issues despite broader shifts in foreign policy priorities.

Germany.

The entry of the far-right party, Alternative for Germany (AfD), into the German parliament made headlines and marked a significant shift in the country's political landscape. The AfD's presence disrupted the ruling coalition led by Chancellor Angela Merkel's CDU, posing challenges for the formation of a new government coalition. Ironically, Merkel's domestic focus and steadfast defense of her 2015 decision to admit large numbers of refugees contributed to the rise of the far-right party, limiting Europe's collective voice on the contentious issue of migrants and refugees.

In contrast to this, the German elections demonstrated an effective strategy for countering the far right. While the economically depressed states, where deep-seated racism and xenophobia persisted since the fall of the Berlin Wall, saw significant support for the AfD, prosperous Bavaria presented a different picture. In Bavaria, the AfD garnered the most votes outside economically challenged regions. Interestingly, the ruling coalition in Bavaria, led by the CSU, had incorporated more elements of right-wing populism than Merkel's CDU. This outcome underscored the notion that a robust battle of ideas can prove more effective in coun-

tering far-right ideologies than mere political opportunism. The results suggested that engaging in meaningful ideological debates can serve as a potent tool in resisting the rise of far-right movements.

Central Europe.

Central Europe has emerged as a fertile ground for populist movements, with some leaders capitalizing on fears of migrants across the continent to weaken checks and balances on their own power. Despite this trend, opposition to populism has been evident in the region.

In Poland, President Andrzej Duda faced widespread public protests and international criticism when the government attempted to undermine the independence of the judiciary and the rule of law. Duda, responding to the pressure, blocked the government's efforts. However, the alternative proposal he subsequently put forth was also deemed flawed.

In Hungary, the threat of potential European Union (EU) sanctions, coupled with international condemnation, including from the United States, disrupted government plans to close the Central European University. The university was considered a bastion of independent thought, standing in opposition to the "illiberal democracy" advocated by Prime Minister Viktor Orbán. The interference with the university sparked a backlash from various quarters, demonstrating that international pressure and criticism can play a role in curbing populist tendencies even in regions where such movements have gained traction.

Concerns about Poland's encroachments on democracy are gaining recognition within European institutions and among certain EU member states. There is a growing understanding that these actions pose a threat not only to Poland but also to the entire European Union. Given that both Poland and Hungary are significant beneficiaries of funding from the EU budget, discussions have arisen regarding the appropriateness of tying financial assistance to adherence to the core values of the European Union. This debate reflects a broader consideration of how the EU can address challenges to democratic principles within its member states and maintain the integrity of the union.

Latin America.

In Latin America, Venezuelan President Nicolas Maduro continued to dismantle democracy and undermine the economy, all under the guise of protecting the disenfranchised from supposed "imperialists." However, as his regime became more brutal and autocratic, the corruption and economic mismanagement became increasingly evident. Despite having substantial oil reserves, the nation struggled with poverty, exacerbated by rampant hyperinflation that turned even basic necessities like food and medicine into unattainable luxuries for many.

In response to these challenges, citizens took to the streets in large numbers, expressing their discontent. Government officials even defected in some instances. Breaking with tradition, an unprecedented number of Latin American states openly condemned the repression in Venezuela. Furthermore, other international actors, including the European Union, joined in expressing criticism against Maduro's regime for its assault on

democracy and its adverse impact on the Venezuelan economy.

Nicolas Maduro has managed to cling to power primarily through brutal repression, utilizing the support of a compliant Supreme Court and a Constitutional Assembly that he established to wrest legislative power from the opposition-controlled National Assembly. This has enabled Maduro to launch a comprehensive crackdown on dissent. Despite these measures, the country continues to spiral into poverty, and the duration of the people's tolerance for the current leader remains uncertain.

In addition to political challenges, some modern populist leaders promote a misogynistic agenda. For example, Russia decriminalized certain instances of domestic violence last year. Poland, which already has one of the most restrictive abortion legislations in Europe, has further restricted the availability of emergency contraception. These developments underscore the broader implications of populist movements on issues related to human rights and gender equality.

Under the administration of Donald Trump, the United States reinstated and expanded the Global Gag Rule, a policy dating back to the Reagan era. This rule prohibits funding for foreign non-governmental organizations (NGOs) that engage in abortion-related activities, leading to substantial reductions in U.S. funding for crucial healthcare services for women and girls outside the United States.

Women's Rights.

In response to these changes, the Women's March, initially sparked by Trump's victory in the U.S., has evolved into a global movement. It mobilizes millions of people worldwide in support of women's rights, reflecting a broader international response to policy shifts that impact reproductive health and access to essential healthcare services.

Both Canadian Prime Minister Justin Trudeau and French President Emmanuel Macron have actively portrayed themselves as advocates for the feminist agenda. Canada has prioritized gender equality in its aid programs, while France has announced new measures to address gender-based violence and sexual harassment. Additionally, the governments of the Netherlands, Belgium, and Scandinavian countries have taken the lead in establishing an international fund to support reproductive rights, aiming to fill the funding gap left by the U.S. position on such issues.

Sweden, in particular, has pursued a "feminist foreign policy," prioritizing the rights of women and girls in its diplomatic engagements, even in challenging contexts like Saudi Arabia. These initiatives reflect a growing international commitment to advancing gender equality and women's rights on a global scale.

Under the pressure of women's rights activists, Tunisia, Jordan, and Lebanon have all abolished criminal provisions that allowed rapists to evade punishment by marrying the victim. These legal reforms mark significant steps forward in addressing issues related to sexual violence and ensuring justice for survivors. The changes reflect a broader global movement advocating for the elimination of laws that perpetuate gender-based violence and discrimination against women.

LGBT individuals

Governments seeking support from conservative voters have often targeted sexual and gender minorities as a means of distraction from their own failures. Leaders such as Vladimir Putin, Abdel Fattah el-Sisi, and Robert Mugabe have cultivated phobias towards lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) individuals for political advantage. In countries like Indonesia, Tanzania, and Azerbaijan, law enforcement agencies have acted with impunity, apprehending LGBT individuals in public places and invading private properties. These actions reflect a pattern of discrimination and persecution against sexual and gender minorities in various parts of the world.

The targeted persecution of LGBT individuals often serves as an indicator that a government is facing challenges or dissatisfaction with its policies. However, there is a diminishing confidence that homophobic campaigns will receive unconditional approval, as there is a growing global awareness and advocacy against discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity. The increasing visibility of LGBTQ+ rights movements and international condemnation of human rights violations against sexual and gender minorities contribute to a changing landscape where such discriminatory campaigns face greater scrutiny and opposition.

The majority of Latin American states have firmly aligned themselves with supporters of LGBT rights at international forums, joining countries like Japan and many others in Europe and North America. In recent years, several countries, including Mozambique, Belize, Nauru, and the Seychelles, have decriminalized same-sex relationships. This trend reflects a broader global shift towards recognizing and protecting the rights of the LGBTQ+ community, although challenges and opposition persist in various regions.

The global trend toward recognizing and advocating for LGBTQ+ rights has also had an impact in Russia. The international outcry over the detentions, torture, forced disappearances, and murders inflicted on gay individuals in Chechnya by local security forces in the spring of 2017 prompted global condemnation. The widespread outrage compelled Russian President Vladimir Putin to intervene, instructing his ally Ramzan Kadyrov to halt the mass hunt for gays in Chechnya.

However, in other situations, external considerations have impeded effective action. For instance, in the case of the persecution of LGBTQ+ people in Egypt, some donors hesitated to raise challenging questions for fear of offending an ally in the fight against terrorism. This underscores the complex dynamics and challenges that persist in efforts to address LGBTQ+ rights globally.

Conclusion. The global rise of populist movements has sparked debates and challenges across various regions, impacting issues ranging from democracy and human rights to gender equality and LGBTQ+ rights. Drawing parallels with events like the election of Donald Trump in the United States, the resistance against regressive policies highlights the pivotal role of civil society, activists, journalists, lawyers, and concerned citizens in safeguarding principles of inclusiv-

ity, human rights, and social justice. The far-right Alternative for Germany (AfD) entering the German parliament and disruptions in the ruling coalition exemplify the impact of populism in reshaping political landscapes. The German experience suggests that meaningful ideological debates can effectively counter far-right ideologies, emphasizing the importance of ideas over political opportunism. In Central Europe, Poland and Hungary face scrutiny for potential threats to democracy, leading to discussions on tying EU assistance to adherence to core values. This demonstrates a growing awareness of the need to address challenges to democratic principles within the EU and maintain the union's integrity. In Latin America, the case of Venezuela illustrates the consequences of populist leadership on democracy and economic stability, triggering domestic protests and international condemnation. The response to the repression in Venezuela highlights the global commitment to human rights, even in the face of authoritarian rule. On issues of gender and sexual minorities, global movements, such as the Women's March and international initiatives promoting reproductive rights, showcase the resilience and unity in advocating for women's rights. Legal reforms in several countries abolishing provisions that allowed rapists to evade punishment by marrying victims represent positive steps toward justice. While challenges persist, the changing landscape indicates a global shift toward recognizing and protecting LGBTQ+ rights. Instances like the Chechnya persecution highlight the importance of international condemnation, although challenges, such as diplomatic considerations, continue to impede comprehensive action.

In essence, the complex and interconnected issues arising from populist movements underscore the need for continued international collaboration, advocacy, and a commitment to principles of democracy, human rights, and equality. The evolving global response suggests that, despite challenges, collective efforts can shape a more inclusive and just world.

References

1. Ершова Е., Демышева А., Любавина С., (2021). "Национальное объединение": третья политическая сила Франции в начале 2000-х. <https://spb.hse.ru/ixtati/news/452520399.html>
2. Рубан Л. (2021). "Неопределенность французской политической жизни: Сдвиг вправо и кризис представительной демократии"
3. Канинская Г. (2018). Метаболизмы правого популизма во Франции XXI века.
4. Всемирный доклад 2018. "Популизм: несостоявшийся триумф?" <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2018/country-chapters/313399>
5. Володин А. (2020). "Феномен «нового популизма»: американское измерение"
6. Волкова И. В. (1992). "Популизм и консерватизм: К истории Американской политической мысли конца XIX века". Издательство МГУ.
7. Артемий Магун (2021г.). "Что такое популизм и каковы его отношения с демократией?". <https://vlast.kz/politika/44735-cto-takoe-populizm-i-kakovy-ego-otnosenia-s-demokratiej.html>

8. Волкова И. В. (1992). "Популизм и консерватизм: К истории Американской политической мысли конца XIX века". Издательство МГТУ.
9. Randall G. Holcombe (2021). "Populism. Promises and Problems" Published By: Independent Institute.
10. Jan-Werner Müller (2017). "What is Populism?" Philadelphia, University of Pennsylvania.
11. Berman, Sheri (11 May 2021). "The Causes of Populism in the West". Annual Review of Political Science.
12. Camus, Jean-Yves; Lebourg, Nicolas (20 March 2017). Far-Right Politics in Europe. Harvard University Press.
13. Campani, Giovanna; Fabelo Concepción, Sunamis; Rodriguez Soler, Angel; Sánchez Savín, Claudia (December 2022). "The Rise of Donald Trump Right-Wing Populism in the United States: Middle American Radicalism and Anti-Immigration Discourse". Societies.
14. North, Bonnie. (2017) "The Rise of Right-Wing Nationalist Political Parties in Europe"
15. Wodak, R.E., Krzyzanowski, M. (2017) "Right-wing populism in Europe and USA". Journal of Language and Politics.
16. Wodak, R.E. (2019) "The Micro-Politics of Right-wing Populism". Published: Populism and Citizenship
17. Wodak, R., Khosravinik, M. (2013) "Dynamics of Discourse and Politics in Right-wing Populism in Europe and Beyond: An Introduction". Published: Rightwing Populism in Europe: Politics and Discourse